

THE RELATIONSHIP OF STUDENT YOUTH TO HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AND SPORTS

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ABSTRACT

It is known to us that in the next two years, the emergence of the worldwide "COVID-19" coronavirus pandemic has shown that the level of health of the population, as well as living a healthy life is weak in Uzbekistan, among other countries of the world.

"COVID-19" coronavirus infection first of all adversely affected the health of our citizens suffering from diseases of the cardiovascular and respiratory tract, as well as obesity (excess weight). As a result, today's pandemic caused many of our citizens to turn a blind eye to the untimely world among us.

All of us, having made a more serious conclusion, refuse harmful habits, constantly engage in mass sports, adhere to the principles of proper nutrition, in particular those that have a lot of salt, sugar and fat in their composition, and do not eat pastries and sweets, bakery products more than the norm, in a word, it is necessary that we must turn a healthy lifestyle into [2].

The rules of a healthy lifestyle serve to ensure the health of a person, the initial profile of diseases is recognized as an excellent factor of Health. Healthy lifestyle this is not only a medical and biological activity, but also a rational satisfaction of physical and spiritual needs, the formation

of a person's personal culture and education. This is a high medical activity, the opportunity to perform their professional and social duties regardless of the political and economic situation in the country.

When we say a healthy lifestyle, the typical life form of a person every day is understood. Its action strengthens, improves the body, improves the social and professional functions of the body. The content of a healthy lifestyle consists of work and rest, sleep hygiene, nutrition hygiene, exercise, self-esteem, being able to behave in a relationship with people, etc.

In the formation of a healthy lifestyle among students, first of all, strengthen health, change the shape of life, improve hygienic knowledge increase, fight harmful habits, formulate a healthy diet, coping with the unfavorable aspects of hypodynamia and life situations it consists in teaching [7].

Using physical exercises in the treatment of diseases all over the world, it is achieved not

only to stop the pathological process of the body, but also to completely eliminate it.

Physical education exercises have been used since very ancient times by mankind for the purpose of maintaining health, treating various diseases, preventing them and longevity [6].

The concept of a healthy lifestyle of a person is the most acceptable within the definitions-academic Y.P.Lisitsin expressed definition: "a healthy lifestyle is a way of life activity aimed at maintaining and strengthening the health of a person".

"Popularization of physical education and sports in our country is defined as one of the important directions of social policy. Because sport is the top deciding healthy lifestyle in society by strengthening the health of the population, educating the younger generation as healthy and harmonious. It prevents various diseases, harmful habits among young people. Sport also plays an important role in the formation of high culture, feelings of patriotism. The achievements in this area will introduce the country to the world, give pride to all compatriots"[3].

Physical education is a part of culture that consists of the sum of values, norms and knowledge that are created and used by society for the purpose of physical education of a person, physical development and physical training, improvement of his abilities and activity, formation of skills of a healthy lifestyle, social adaptation [1].

Research methods and organization. At present, the attitude of the students

towards the healthy lifestyle of the young people and their regular activities in sports to study and classify it, the compliance of the students with the healthy lifestyle of the Gulistan State University and their fitness for sports has been studied on the basis of the questionnaire.

Questionnaire questions and procedure for its conduct.

Questions for students who are constantly engaged in physical education and sports:

1. Do regular sports activities strengthen human health?
2. Are you constantly engaged in sports?
3. Do you always focus on timely and proper nutrition?
4. Do you consume harmful habits (tobacco and alcohol products)?
5. Do you follow the agenda (8 hours of sleep)?
6. Do you follow the rules of personal hygiene (washing hands before and after eating, cleaning teeth before and after eating, clean clothes, in general, strict adherence to cleanliness)?
7. Do regular sports activities raise a person's mood and psyche?
8. Did you notice in yourself its symptoms when the "COVID-19" virus spread in the world?

It was necessary to answer the above questions with 4 variants: "Yes", "No", "I do not know" and "I find it difficult to answer". The survey was conducted among university students in January 2022. 200 students participated in the questionnaire.

Results and their discussion.

The results of the Student Youth Survey are presented in the table below:

Questions	I see	No	I do not know	To answer tough
1	190	2	3	5
2	48	152	-	-
3	42	108	23	27
4	10	181	-	9
5	37	103	42	18
6	152	25	-	23
7	138	13	25	24
8	57	75	46	22

95% of the students answered yes to the question of whether constant sports activities strengthen human health.

It became known that 76% of students are constantly engaged in sports

More than 50% of students do not always focus on timely and proper nutrition.

It was found that 90.5% of students were far from consuming tobacco and alcohol products, 5% were suffering from responding to YES students.

5-question i.e. 8 hours of sleep on the agenda 18.5% of students adhere. While 51.5% do not follow at all. Those who had difficulty answering, scored 9%, those who answered "I do not know", 21%.

The compliance of students with the rules of personal hygiene was 76%. And those who were hard to answer, dropped 11.5%.

On the question of whether it raises the mood and psyche of a person as a result of regular sports activities, 69% of students showed "Yes", 6.5% said "No", 12.5% said "I do not know", and 12% said those who had difficulty responding.

Those who felt the symptoms of the " COVID-19 " virus included 28.5%, while those who

did not know were 23%, 11% had difficulty responding. And 37.5% said they would say "no."

The results of our study showed that adherence to a healthy lifestyle among students and their regular involvement in sports are becoming irregular. But physical education and sports, along with a healthy lifestyle have proven on a scientific basis that there are a thousand to be conducted together. But it is very important to learn that regular sports training under each specific condition has a positive impact on health, and this issue is under constant control, which is of great practical importance. Because in some cases, the wrong planning of training nagruzki and the use of more volume than the physical and functional capacity of the participants can lead to unpleasant consequences.

Pedagogical research should be conducted in order to study this problem in more depth, identify ways to eliminate existing defects in this regard, as well as develop the necessary practical recommendations.

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